

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Indonesia's maritime strategy for realizing the world's axis facing China's maritime silk road policy

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Abstract

The World Maritime Axis Policy (WMA) initiated by the Government of Indonesia focuses on Indonesia's national development based on activities at sea, upholding the sovereignty of the sea territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, revitalizing the maritime economic sectors, strengthening and developing maritime connectivity. This is very dynamic when faced with China's Maritime Silk Road (MSR) policy. The purpose of this research is to obtain a mapping of the opportunities and threats of the maritime sector in Indonesia in the dynamics of the World Maritime Axis and China's Maritime Silk Road and to obtain the formulation of Indonesia's strategy in realizing the World Maritime Axis which is faced with the Silk Road policy arithmetic of China. The method used is an in-depth review analysis of material and theory related to the research topic. The results obtained are a strategy that must be carried out by the Government of Indonesia, especially the World Maritime Axis Policy towards China's Maritime Silk Road policy which has several advantages and threats. Indonesia took the best way to take advantage of China's offer of the Maritime Silk Road by joining the AIIB to realize the World Maritime Axis policy. Furthermore, the Strengthening Strategy for the Indonesian Navy is very necessary for maintaining the security stability of the maritime border area. The Indonesian Navy occupies a strategic position and portion to strive for optimal implementation of the world's maritime vision. Carrying out operations with the support of the main tools of a sophisticated defense system, and speeding up an escort for the government to achieve its vision of Naval Diplomacy effectively.

Keywords: Global Maritime Strategy; Indonesia's world maritime axis; China's Maritime silk road

1. Introduction

Indonesia is an archipelagic country with a total of 17,499 islands a sea area of 93,000 square kilometers and a coastline of 81 thousand square kilometers. The water area includes archipelagic waters, a territorial sea, and the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of 6,159,032 square kilometers. Flanked by the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean as well as the Asian Continent and the Australian Continent, Indonesia has 39 straits that have links with other straits in the Asian region. Indonesia has four of the nine *choke points* in the world. The four *choke points* referred to here are the Malacca Strait, Makassar Strait, Sunda Strait, and Lombok Strait and the four straits are often used as international shipping lanes. From all this, Indonesia has become a regional *barometer* and key to the stability of Indonesian waters (Ahmadi & Herdiawan, 2019).

The World Maritime Axis Policy (WMA) initiated by the President of Indonesia has become one of the main focuses of national development. The Maritime Axis that was initiated focused on Indonesia's national development based on activities at sea. Upholding the sovereignty of the sea territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, revitalizing the marine economic sectors, strengthening and developing maritime connectivity, rehabilitation of environmental damage and *biodiversity conservation*, as well as increasing the quality and quantity of marine human

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resources (HR) are the main programs in the administration of the President of Indonesia to realize Indonesia as the world's maritime axis (Bandono et al, 2019).

Seeing the basic concept of the pillars of the maritime axis, in implementing the concept of the maritime axis, it should prioritize the implementation of sovereignty at sea. Completion of maritime boundaries and strengthening of defense at sea – ensuring the effect of *deterrence* and control of the sea to ensure the use of the sea for its own interests (sea control) and prevent the use of the sea for interests other than Indonesia (Ahmadi et al, 2017). If sovereignty at sea is achieved and maintained, it will be easier to implement the other pillars. Indonesia is a country that loves peace, but the principle of *si vis Pacem, para bellum* (if you want peace, you have to be ready for war) needs to be implemented to strengthen Indonesia's maritime sovereignty. After our maritime sovereignty is fulfilled and maintained, then may we use the principle of *si vis Pacem, para pactum* (if you want peace, keep the peace).

Before the Maritime Axis policy was initiated by President Joko Widodo, China had sparked the concept of the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) President Xi Jinping in 2013. MSR had been proclaimed by China for international cooperation so that it would involve more developing countries to mutually participate in building their economies (Susilo et al, 2020). And implementing economic development on a peaceful path with the motto "*Receiving harmony with diversity*" or tolerance and harmony in diversity. Now we can be said to live in the era of globalization, the relationship between locations and regions in parts of the world has also been comfortable and fast to integrate the world economy. After serving as President of China, Xi Jinping continues to make efforts to expand China's role at the *state-system level*. One of the initiatives initiated by President Xi is to rebuild the glory of the Chinese Silk Road. The Silk Road itself is an ancient trading road that was pioneered in 206 BC, during the Han Dynasty. In its heyday, the Silk Road stretched for more than 6000 kilometers connecting China with western civilization (Herdiawan & Ahmadi, 2019).

Concerning the maritime axis policy issued by the President of Indonesia, of course, China's MSR policy can be a stepping stone to realizing Indonesia as a WMA. However, this can also be detrimental to Indonesia or ASEAN countries, which are organizations of which Indonesia is a member. The reason is that the conflict in the South China Sea, Indonesia is a country that is not directly involved in the conflict (Nugroho et al, 2019). This has put Indonesia in a dilemma between making MSR a springboard to realize Indonesia's WMA or Indonesia having to fend for itself in realizing these ideals. If Indonesia uses China's MSR as its stepping stone, ASEAN will likely be hit by divisions and Indonesia will likely become China's next target in disputes in the South China Sea region. On this basis, how are Indonesia's efforts to realize the World Maritime Axis during China's Maritime Silk Road policy (Setiadji et al, 2019)?

Based on this background, the problem statements in this research are: (1) How to map the opportunities and threats of the maritime sector in Indonesia in the dynamics of the World Maritime Axis (WMA) and China's Maritime Silk Road (MSR) domestic and global maritime environment (2) How formulating Indonesia's strategy in realizing the World Maritime Axis (WMA) in the face of the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) policy China.

The purpose of this research is to obtain a mapping of opportunities and threats to the maritime sector in Indonesia in the dynamics of the World Maritime Axis (WMA) and China's Maritime Silk Road (MSR) and to obtain formulations of Indonesia's strategy in realizing the World Maritime Axis (WMA) faced on the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) policy China. This is very necessary because the development of strategic and global dynamics and the domestic environment are very influential in national maritime conditions. The systematics in this study are Part 1 discussing the Background, Part 2 Reviewing Material, Part 3 concerning Results and Discussion and Part 4 Conclusions, and Part 5 Managerial Implications.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Strategy Theory

In this study, the writer will use strategy theory. Strategy is a method used to achieve a victory or a goal. There are various definitions from experts regarding strategy. Gregory D. Foster (2000) in his article entitled *A Conceptual Foundation for the Development of Strategy* explains strategy is an action plan that has been formed to achieve something; shared goals with the system in the form of steps to achieve them, which means the strategy is the effectiveness of using *power*. These steps can use all instruments of force, both military and non-military, which are coordinated within a country or alliance to achieve the intended object (Baylis, 2002).

In realizing its World Maritime Axis, Indonesia has made several efforts that are considered very strategic. Creation of the Sea Highway by utilizing inter-island connectivity to the utilization of natural resources in the marine sector in Indonesia. Of course, these steps are taken to achieve the World Maritime Axis. In addition to all that, Indonesia is

cooperating with China in infrastructure development to accelerate the construction of its maritime highway to achieve the maritime axis of the world.

2.2. Geopolitical Theory

Next, the writer will use geopolitics from Alfred Thayer Mahan (2004). Mahan said that "whoever controls the sea, then he controls the world". Concerning the geographic location of a country, two aspects are important to understand. First, the location of a country facing many seas with good communication between its parts so that it is difficult for the enemy to conquer it, secondly, the location of a country in the form of islands that are in front of a continent or land, so that it is like fortifying its land. In this case, the natural ports owned by the country concerned function completely beneficially, both for trade and for its navy. However, in this case, it should be noted that the convenience of the inland areas that can be reached from the coasts can also be detrimental to the country in times of war. This is related to government policies, utilization density population, and attitude to the country's neighbor.

AT Mahan (2004) underlined, that *Sea Power* or sea power is a very important element for the glory of a nation (Geoffrey, 2004). Conversely, if the forces at sea are not empowered, it will result in a great loss to the country or undermine the nation. AT Mahan stated that the Power of the Sea is: "*All that tends to make a people great upon the sea or by sea*". An example is the rise of British sea power in his time. England was ideally situated at the crossroads of European trade routes. The British were able to take advantage of and secure their trade routes from the use of the sea by opposing parties. Apart from that, Britain's geographical position provides natural protection from enemy invasion and does not require Britain to have a large army force (Geoffrey, 2004).

From the example above, it can be learned that the advantage of geographical position will not appear dominant if a nation does not have a sufficient coastline to build ports, does not have adequate natural resources, and is not supported by a good climate/weather. Besides those perspectives and marine insights from the community are a source of maritime strength and the welfare of the nation. The government's ability to carry out diplomacy and influence other countries has a very significant role in dominating its sea area. The book "*The Influence of Sea Power upon History*", is considered important because this book describes Mahan's thoughts to achieve national power, and explains how to deploy Sea Power to face enemies. What is meant by Sea Power or Sea Power, is synonymous with Maritime Power or Maritime Power. If these powers are empowered, it will increase the Welfare and Security of the State. Besides this, Rear Admiral AT Mahan stated that "Navy superiority is the main requirement to make a big, strong and advanced country". The perpetrators of national defense operations at sea consist of several agencies with the Navy (Navy) as the core force. Sea power consists of the Commercial Fleet, Navy, and Bases. Apart from that, the sea is one unit (*The Sea is all One*), meaning that the sea cannot be fenced, occupied, and defended like land. So that the maritime strategy is mastery at sea, namely by guaranteeing the use of the sea for its interests and closing opportunities for opponents to use it.

AT Mahan's (2004) view of the world as a whole emphasizes the need for unity *of the sea* as a condition for being able to control and control the seas from major bases on land. It is also stated here that there is a need for unitary monitoring of the main bases on land. It is also stated here that there is a need for a monitoring unit for bases from land and air as the main requirement to be able to guarantee the implementation of a monitoring unit for the sea. Sea power and naval strategy, according to Mahan's assessment, depend on several physical-geographical factors, for example, the insular or continental position of a nation and national politics related to issues of sea transportation, trade shipping, and bases outside the region.

2.3. Potential Benefits of the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) by China

The Maritime Silk Road Initiative (MSR) by China was presented at an important point in Indonesia's economic development. Several years earlier Indonesia launched a master plan for long-term economic development, known as the Master Plan for the Acceleration and Expansion of the Indonesian Economy (MP3EI). MP3EI is an ambitious plan, aimed at boosting Indonesia enters the top ten economies by 2025. The plan has three pillars: development of economic corridors or growth centers, strengthening connectivity, and, development of human resources and, national science and technology (Suharyo et al, 2017).

Like MSR, WMA still needs to be further elaborated. Nevertheless, in terms of what has been said so far, among other things, the construction of a sea highway and possibly also the maritime-based economy in general. It is hoped that the construction of the sea highway will include the development of ports in various regions in Indonesia as well as expanding and modernizing the country's shipping industry. Meanwhile, a marine-based economy also includes, among other components, ship/vessel development, repair and maintenance infrastructure and services, fishing, offshore oil exploration and extraction, resource extraction and utilization, marine tourism and recreational activities, and environmental management sea (Suharjo et al, 2019).

WMA is a 'rediscovery' of Indonesia's identity as a maritime nation. Indonesia has long been managed as if it were a continental country which it was not. Indonesia consists of about 17000 islands, between 2000 and 4000 of which are inhabited. In addition, about two-thirds of the country's area is water. There are several possible reasons not to neglect the maritime nature of this country. First, Indonesia's population is concentrated on several large islands. According to the 2010 census, of the 237 million Indonesians in 2010, approximately 57.5 percent lived in Java, 21.3 percent in Sumatra, 7.3 percent in Sulawesi, and 5.8 percent in Kalimantan. This causes the distribution of the economy to be uneven because it only relies on these 4 regions. Second, investment in marine infrastructures such as ports and sea transportation is expensive (Suharjo et al, 2019). This problem is exacerbated further by two factors. The first is the unequal distribution of population and the concentration of economic development in the several islands discussed above. As a result, say ships carrying goods from Java to the eastern part of the country are nearly empty on their return journeys. This is one of the reasons why logistics costs are so high in Indonesia, estimated at around a quarter of the country's gross domestic product. The second factor, until recently PT Pelabuhan Indonesia (PT Pelindo) had a monopoly over the development and management of the country's ports. PT Pelindo may have inefficiently managed the country's ports. *Cabotage* policies are often cited as another factor for high logistics costs indicating that logistical costs have indeed increased since the introduction of the policy and that such combative policies have had a direct bearing on the increase (Reza, 2020).

In general, there are three views on the MSR initiative. The first view argues that MSR is a 'blessing in disguise' because the initiative can fit in with the WMA vision launched by President Joko Widodo at the start of his presidency. In a regional context, MSR promotes further connectivity between countries through its five links (policy, roads, trade, currency, and people). According to a scientist, MSR and WMA will discuss connectivity, security, and diplomacy. Therefore, there is potential for this MSR initiative to transform longstanding disputes over territorial sovereignty, particularly in the South China Sea by using constructive joint activities that will facilitate smooth sea navigation in the area (Nugroho et al, 2020).

In addition, the inclusion of new initiatives such as MSR or becoming one of the founding members of the *Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank* (AIIB) is seen as not limiting the independence of Indonesia's foreign policy. For example, with its participation in AIIB, Indonesia can maintain its participation in existing international financial institutions, such as the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank. In fact, by participating in the new initiative, Indonesia will have more alternatives to serve its national interests. When compared to previous initiatives (MSR) is the first proposal that includes Indonesia in its development (Ahmadi et al, 2017).

2.4. Potential Threats of the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) in Indonesia

Some scientists recommend not rushing to accept the concept, let alone synchronize WMA with MSR, given the conditions discussed above. As one official explained, Indonesia's agreement to join MSR had to be carefully worded in a way that would not be perceived as a tacit acknowledgment of China's nine-track demands. Finally, the scientific group took a stronger stance against the MSR initiative. While they are not outspoken in suggesting that the Indonesian government should reject the MSR proposal, scientists or officials within this group need a better and more comprehensive explanation of the motivations behind the initiative, and how the Chinese government plans to implement MSR in practice. . They research, in particular, trying to use MSR to re-install the ancient *Silk Road*, as they note that the practice is designed around the relationship of children between the center/superior and the periphery/inferior countries (Suharyo et al, 2017).

There is a concern that this MSR will be used as an instrument to divide the country into a group of profitable people (since they joined MSR) and a group of people who are not profitable (because they did not join). They further worry that countries on the favorable list will have to pay China certain concessions, such as granting them access to local markets that may be unprofitable for them. Indonesia does not yet have sufficient capacity to explore its resources, especially in the sea. The implementation of MSR is feared to provide too many concessions and opportunities to explore the EEZ in Indonesia because China has advanced maritime technology much better and Indonesia is not ready with legal instruments to protect itself from exploitative practices (Suharjo, 2019).

Stakeholders also see parallels between the MSR concept and the pearl concept, whereby MSR will be part of a strategy to secure China's military and commercial routes at sea, and its maritime communication lines (SLOC) *which* in turn are aimed at addressing India's expansion in the region. While MSR is understood to be an initiative designed to promote connectivity, there are concerns it could be used as another instrument to absorb Indonesia's natural resources at a price favorable to the Chinese. Even more worrying, as China continues to seek to expand its energy resources abroad, neighboring countries keep a close eye on China's growing military might. There is a growing concern that the strong

interest in protecting its energy security will encourage the expansion of China's military influence by enhancing its military capabilities as an effective instrument to support such activities (Ahmadi & Herdiawan, 2019).

While Indonesia is not opposed to China's naval expansion, Indonesia needs to see consistency in China's actions which have so far given the impression that China is becoming an assertive power that often flexes its military muscles to apply its unilateral claims to certain seas that are also claimed by other countries. Therefore, Indonesia questions whether the implementation of the MSR initiative will be compatible with China's efforts to improve cooperation in the region - and therefore work in tandem with potential actions to establish a *Code of Conduct* (CoC) in the South China Sea - and thus reflect that China's rise is the peace that must entertain all actors in this region. Indonesia must also examine whether in this MSR initiative China intends to treat the countries it invites as equal partners or whether it will implement a historical policy of child relations that has turned countries like Indonesia into peripheral countries. If the latter is ongoing, then the connectivity that will be built through MSR will only serve China's interests rather than bring mutual benefits to everyone. Such scenarios need to be anticipated before MSR can be accepted.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The Important Meaning of the Maritime Silk Road (MSR) for Indonesia and China

In terms of prospects, MSR's plan intersects with the WMA Doctrine, wherein the development plan of each idea tends to be integral and complementary. In other words, both MSR and WMA are not contradictory but can cooperate, especially regarding the issue of providing funds for infrastructure development. In this regard, Indonesia is also very open to channels of funds from abroad, either in the form of a *shared budget* or entirely from funding from *the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank* (AIIB). To realize the vision of the World Maritime Axis (WMA) Indonesia joined (AIIB) and proposed as one of the founding countries, so that the funds needed to achieve WMA can be achieved from Chinese assistance, shared budget among another donor/investor countries, or fully financed from disbursement AIIB funds. If this plan goes according to the scenario above - with AIIB as the wrong source of fund development - so could be said that the WMA doctrine by Indonesia becomes an inseparable part of China's MSR. The concept of the Indonesian maritime toll road can be developed into the MSR super maritime highway project.

Based on political analysis, Indonesia must adapt to China's MSR materialization by insisting on the formation of AIIB in Jakarta. Even though Jin Liqun is now still the general secretary of AIIB who was elected on October 24 2014 in Beijing, Indonesia must continue to insist on placing several executive functions in AIIB to balance Indonesia's *vital interest* in the growth of MSR. Not only that, Indonesia must then improve its maritime defense system with the latest technology to secure its sea and sea communication lines, and continue to monitor the flow of traffic in its maritime territory.

Both Indonesia and China have their respective strategies and interests in the MSR and WMA discourse. As has been explained, China's economic, political, security, and socio-cultural interests are very large for the realization of MSR. Planning for the development strategy and direction for the realization of MSR also tend to be clearer than WMA by Indonesia. Therefore, the thing that needs further review is whether China or Indonesia can align their ideas and interests so that they are in line with each other and in line with the interests of other countries involved in the region.

Highlighting the use of China's MSR by Indonesia, University of Indonesia (UI) Defense analyst Dr. Connie Rahakundini Bakrie (2020) believes that this step should not be seen as a threat. Because this can encourage Indonesia to build an independent maritime power because geographically, Indonesia is very strategic as the axis or axis of shipping and world trade routes. How can this strategic position be utilized by China or other maritime countries, then Indonesia's Homework is how Indonesia can immediately benefit as much as possible, supported by the capabilities that must be built and the opportunities that exist. Considering that a maritime country is a country that can utilize and manage the sea, both in terms of space and natural wealth, and strategic location with its technological, scientific, and equipment capabilities, it refers to Alfred Thayer Mahan (2004) said: *"If a country imagines having a long seaboard, but entirely without a harbor, such a country can have no sea trade of its own, no shipping, no numerous navy, and deep harbors are a source of strength and wealth."*

3.2. Indonesia's Strategy in Realizing the World Maritime Axis Confronted China's Maritime Silk Road

- The concept of the sea highway can overcome the main problems of sea transportation related to the imbalance in the volume of goods transported between the western and eastern regions of Indonesia. This concept can be an effective solution in preventing empty capacity ships from sailing from one place to another and is expected to create an efficient and integrated goods distribution system. The high cost of logistics in Indonesia is a burden for logistics service providers, which of course also has an impact on manufacturing companies. Transportation

costs arise from the process of supplying raw materials to the process most downstream from chain supply, ie delivery of goods so to the consumer. Inefficiency and limited facilities in port activities cause a lot of additional costs that must be incurred.

- Currently, the number of main ports in Indonesia has reached 33 units which are equipped with 217 collecting ports and 990 feeder ports. The policy plan, to develop maritime connectivity through sea tolls, deep seaports, logistics, the shipping industry, and maritime tourism in the short term is carried out by increasing the capacity of four main ports, namely Belawan, Tanjung Priok, Tanjung Perak, and Makassar. Meanwhile, in the long term, all major ports and feeder ports will become the backbone of the domestic shipping network and part of the international shipping network for the distribution of goods.
- During the administration period of Indonesian President Joko Widodo and Vice President Jusuf Kalla, it is planned to increase the capacity of 24 ports to support the sea highway consisting of 5 hub ports and 19 feeder ports. The ports that are the sea highway hubs consist of Belawan/ Kuala Tanjung Ports, Tanjung Priok, Tanjung Perak, Makassar, and Bitung. Ports that serve as sea highway feeders consist of the Ports of Malahayati, Batam, Jambi, Palembang, Panjang, Teluk Bayur, Tanjung Emas, Pontianak, Banjarmasin, Sampit, Balikpapan/Kariangau, Samarinda/Palaran, Tenau/Kupang, Pantoloan, Ternate, Kendari, Sorong, Ambon, and Jayapura.
- The maritime connectivity policy in the form of sea highway development has a focus and target. The focus in 2014 is to meet the needs of pioneer shipping, while the target in the fifth year is to realize a sea transportation system capable of reducing logistics costs to 20 percent of gross domestic product, growing the national shipping fleet from 10 to 30 percent, rejuvenating national ships by reducing the number vessels over 25 years from 70 percent to 50 percent, and reduced port service time at main ports from 6 to 7 days to 3 to 4 days. This target is very likely to be achieved if several important steps are carried out, especially cross-sectoral planning, as well as involving local and regional governments Public.
- The joining of Indonesia as a member of the AIIB is an interesting thing to study, seeing that Indonesia has previously joined several international financial institutions, both regional scales such as the ASEAN Development Bank, and international scales such as the World Bank which have collaborated with Indonesia for quite some time long. Indonesia made AIIB an extension of Indonesia's need to achieve its national interests in increasing economic prosperity. AIIB which was formed specifically to provide infrastructure development loans in the Asian region will provide distinct benefits for Indonesia, as the largest maritime country in the Southeast Asian region, and will make Indonesia a partner that is reckoned with by AIIB. Indonesia then agreed to join AIIB and proposed as one of the countries founding fathers, so that funds needed to reach Axis Maritime World can be achieved from Chinese aid, shared budget between other donors/investor countries, or fully financed from AIIB funding.
- Indonesia carries WMA to be at the forefront of Indonesia's national interests domestically and internationally. Based on this, various risks and opportunities from the maritime sector are developed to strengthen and achieve security to help shape world stability. This strategy is placed in the maritime domain in the context of the problem. It is formed and carried out with an approach based on the objectives to be achieved in the future. In the end, it is the structure of government that will determine the effectiveness and efficiency of structuring the Indonesian maritime sector. The problems faced by the majority are threats to resources, in the form of crime, terrorism to crimes against humanity. So it requires strong regulations and clear international policies as well as comprehensive global cooperation aimed at shared security. The maritime domain is very complex in the international system, where Indonesia needs to play a diplomatic role and strengthen military and industrial capabilities defense.
- The Indonesian Navy occupies a strategic position and portion to strive for optimal implementation of the world's maritime vision. Carrying out operations with the support of sophisticated Alutsista equipment will speed up an escort for the government to achieve this vision, provide an overview for other countries and build an effective implementation of diplomacy (Naval Diplomacy). The government and navy can make several efforts, including modernization, build-up, and naval deployment. The dynamics that are developing also need to be a response for Indonesia in managing the achievement of the world's maritime vision. The turmoil in the South China Sea, which so far has not found a bright spot, has become the ground for Indonesia's maritime diplomacy sustainably. Preparing strategic resources and strengthening the armed forces is a form of effective collaboration that must be put forward in the next ten years.

4. Conclusion

The World Maritime Axis Policy initiated by the President of Indonesia which is in the midst of China's Maritime Silk Road policy has several advantages and threats. These various advantages and threats have made Indonesia think hard

to realize its World Maritime Axis. Indonesia took the path of taking advantage of China's offer of the Maritime Silk Road by joining the AIIB to realize its World Maritime Axis policy.

The World Maritime Axis certainly requires large funds. These large funds were obtained from several investments from foreign countries, one of which came from China, which at that time also sparked its Maritime Silk Road. This impact is in the form of assistance in the form of development that can support the Sea Highway. However, Indonesia must see the negative impact, namely in the maritime security sector. Maritime security is in the form of territorial threats to Indonesia which may be disputed by China considering that China is a country that is very ambitious to control the South China Sea region. So Indonesia needs to strengthen the strength of the Indonesian Navy in supervising its maritime sovereignty.

Managerial implications

Strengthening the Indonesian Navy is very necessary for maintaining security stability in Indonesia's border areas. The Indonesian Navy occupies a strategic position and portion to strive for optimal implementation of the world's maritime vision. Carrying out operations with the *support* of sophisticated Alutsista equipment will speed up an escort for the government to achieve this vision, provide an overview for other countries and build an effective implementation of diplomacy (*Naval Diplomacy*). The government and navy can make several efforts, including *modernization, build-up, and naval deployment*. The dynamics that are developing also need to be a response for Indonesia in managing the achievement of the maritime vision world.

The things above are the strategies adopted by Indonesia in realizing its World Maritime Axis in China's Maritime Silk Road Policy. Of course, this is done to see the stability of infrastructure development and maintain security stability in Indonesia. Until now there has been no significant movement in these strategies. Indonesia needs to be prepared in all respects both internally and externally Indonesia.

Compliance with ethical standards

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